

Legal Overview Human Genetics and Genomics: Spain

[WP2 – Human Genetics and Genomics]

Lead contributor	Javier Valls Prieto, University of Granada jvalls@ugr.es
Due date	8 December 2018
Delivery date	29 March 2019
Type	Report
Dissemination level	PU = Public
Keywords	Legal analysis, human genetics, genomics, genetic testing, genetic screening, gene editing

The SIENNA project - *Stakeholder-informed ethics for new technologies with high socio-economic and human rights impact* - has received funding under the European Union's H2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 741716.

© SIENNA, 2019

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

Executive Summary

The main goal of this report is an approach on how genetics and genomics are regulated in Spain in the scope of task 2.2 of the SIENNA project. With that aim 6 questions are addressed and will be answered from different perspectives (legal, legal scholarship and new legal motion in this area).

Spain has several Acts that regulate all the topics of this task that means, we have to make an analysis bases in around 7 acts, making the task complicated in the way that some of the six questions do not have a concrete answer.

This report has four different parts. The first one is an approach to the Spanish law system in general and how the international treaties have been adopted, or not, to the national law system. We can find that nearly all international norms have been adapted into an act. In general, we can say that Spain has a big influence in genetics and genomics from the international agreement on this topic. Nearly all laws have been created after an International treaty.

The second section we make a review of the legal doctrine. In Spain there is not many literatures about genetics, genomics and law and most of them are written by doctors, not lawyers. Also, in the second part of this point we make an analysis of the legal corpus and the new legal motions. Some of the most important acts in genetics and genomics have been recently amended, 2015-2017, thus there is no legal motion in this year.

The third part answers the six questions from the legal point of view. There is no general genetic and genomic act in Spain. For that reason we need to play with different norms, State and from the Autonomous Communities, to answer these questions. It is true that we have the Biomedical Research Act as the nucleus of the regulation in genetics and genomics, but not all questions are addressed in that act.

Lastly, in part four we summarise the main discussion points, from scholar, legislative and legal debate, and we make our conclusions about the report from the Spain point of view. There challenges that need a legal change or a different legal perspective. These genetics and genomics technologies develop so fast that the law is not able to find solutions to the new risk and the new challenge that society demand already.

Document history

Version	Date	Description	Reason for change	Distribution
V1	8 June 2018	First Draft	Feedback and further work	Task contributors
V2	8 December 2018	Comments	Feedback and further work	Task leaders

Information in this report that may influence other SIENNA tasks

Linked task	Points of relevance
Task 2.2	This report is part of and, will provide input to deliverable 2.2.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
List of tables.....	5
Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations	5
Table 2 Glossary of terms.....	5
Part I Introduction	8
1. National legal system in context	8
1.1 An overview of Spain legal system.....	8
1.2 Spain and United Nations.....	8
1.3 Spain and UNESCO	8
1.4 Spain and OECD	9
1.5 Spain and CoE	9
2 Objectives of the report.....	10
3. Approach, materials and method	10
3.1 Literature overview	11
3.2 Legal developments	11
3.3 Analysis of legislation for 6 specific questions on genetics and genomics.....	11
4. Scope and Limitations of this report	11
Part II current overview of legal academic publications and legal developments in Country Spain	11
5. Current legal academic debates in the area of genetics and genomics	11
5.1 Current legal academic debates regarding human germline gene editing	11
5.2 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic screening in general	12
5.3 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic testing in general	12
5.4 Current legal academic debates regarding prenatal testing/screening	12
5.5 Current legal academic debates regarding newborn screening	12
5.6 Current legal academic debates regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening	13
6. Legal developments in the area of genetics and genomics.....	13
6.1 Legal developments regarding human germline gene editing.....	13
6.2 Legal developments regarding genetic screening in general	13
6.3 Legal developments regarding genetic testing in general	13
6.4 Legal developments regarding prenatal testing/screening	14
6.5 Legal developments regarding newborn screening.....	14
6.6 Legal developments regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening.....	14
Part III Specific legal considerations on human genetics and genomics	14
7. Human germline gene editing.....	14
8. Genetic screening in general	16
9. Genetic testing in general	18
10. Prenatal testing/screening	18
11 Newborn screening.....	19
12. Advertising of genetic testing or screening	19
Part IV Discussion and conclusions.....	20
13. Discussion	20
14. Conclusions	22

References 24
International law 24
National law 24
Literature 25

List of tables

- **Table 1:** List of acronyms/abbreviations
- **Table 2:** Glossary of terms
- **Table 3:** List of national legislation

Table 1 List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
GT	Genetic testing
DTC	Direct-to-consumer

Table 2 Glossary of terms

Term	Explanation
Genetic Test	A genetic test: is an assay performed to obtain genetic information (directly on DNA or even on other molecules (RNA, proteins), which by extension could give us genetic information.
Genetic Testing	<p>Genetic testing is usually offered to individual patients based on specific individual need on a one-on-one basis (diagnostic testing, prenatal testing, etc. https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/uses). An assay (a genetic test) would be conducted after the clinician has decided to prescribe the test to the specific patient in question.</p> <p>Genetic testing is a type of medical test that identifies changes in chromosomes, genes, or proteins. The results of a genetic test can confirm or rule out a suspected genetic condition or help determine a person's chance of developing or passing on a genetic disorder.¹ Genetic testing could be accessed through a health care provider as part of clinical medical care, or as a service or product offered directly to consumers. Issues genetic testing raises relate to access rights, protection of integrity, medical oversight when these tests are being offered, as well as genetic counselling, and quality.</p> <p>Other questions that relate to genetic testing emerge in the area of advertising and the use of genetic information. In regard to advertising such issues as, for example, whether genetic testing providers are or are not allowed to advertise their offered genetic tests emerge (contrast with a distinction being made for advertising prescription and non-prescription drugs).² In regard to genetic information, such issues as who can access one's genetic information, and how this information could be used for different purposes, for example, life insurance. One of key issues that emerges in this regard is discrimination relating to one's genome.</p>

¹ US National Library of Medicine, <https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/primer/testing/genetic-testing>, accessed 10 July 2018.

² Please consult Louiza Kalokairinou, Pascal Borry, Heidi Carmen Howard, Regulating the advertising of genetic tests in Europe: a balancing act, *Journal of Medical Genetics*, Volume 54, Issue 10.

Genetic Screening	Genetic screening can have a few different meanings that differ based on subtle nuances and contexts, but in general, we contrast genetic screening from genetic testing because screening is offered to an entire group of people (not specific individuals). In particular screening cases, like newborn screening, for example, the screening programme follows public health frameworks (as opposed to genetic testing which is not a public health programme but within a clinical specialty; in countries where public health programmes don't differ so strongly from clinical practice, you may want to ignore this if it confuses you more. Differences between public health programmes and clinical (one patient at a time) programmes could mean differences in how we approach consent and the obligatory nature of any programme). Other than the "group/population" aim of screening programmes, screening programmes can vary hugely in different ways: population/group targeted (population wide? Certain people/mothers at higher risks as a group?) etc.
Gene Editing/Genome Editing	Gene editing is a relatively recent term used for the description of modifying DNA (you may have previously heard in the past recombinant DNA technology or similar terms that all overlap in some fashion); the term gene editing has come along with the advent of particularly powerful and accurate tools like CRISPR-Cas9 (which is a tool that helps to change DNA). Gene editing can also be referred to as genome modification, which is more holistic, if you will as a concept, but addresses the same ideas; it basically includes not only changing individual DNA in one location but also many changes throughout the genome. One can edit genes in somatic cells (which are not inherited) or one could edit genes in gametes or germline cells which are inherited and would pass down, in theory, DNA modifications/edits to future generations. The term human genome germline modification then includes the modification of 1 or many bits of DNA in an inheritable human cell. Many authors also include the replacement of mitochondria from one embryo to another as a type of germline modification, though this can be argued as (not) being very distinct from DNA modification, for the sake of comparison with other studies, we will include it for the purposes of this SIENNA study.

Table 3 List of national legislation

Biomedical Research Act, 14/2007
Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act, 14/2006
Royal Decree 1090/2015 on Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Comities and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research
The Royal Decree 1662/2000 about Health Products for in vitro Diagnosis
Sexual and Reproduction Health and voluntary termination of the pregnancy Act, 2/2010
Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim
Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Products Act, 29/2006

Decree 1/2013 on Genetic Council, Protection of Persons Been Subject of a Genetic Testing and DNA Bank in Andalusia

Articles 159-162 of the Penal Code, Act 10/1995 on the Penal Code

General Health Act, 14/1986

Act Project on Data Protection and Digital Rights Warranties), 2018

Spanish Constitution, 29 December 1978

Royal Decree 53/2013 that establish the basic norms apply to protection of animals used on experimentation and other research aims, included lecturing. In general, it is allowed to use animals in research procedures

Part I Introduction

1. National legal system in context

1.1 An overview of Spain legal system

Spain is a constitutional State with 17 Autonomous Communities (Galicia, Asturias, Cantabria, País Vasco, Navarra, Aragón, Cataluña, Castilla León, La Rioja, Madrid, Castilla la Mancha, País Valenciano, Baleares, Murcia, Extremadura, Andalucía y Canarias) and two autonomous cities (Ceuta y Melilla). The Constitution gives separate powers to the State and to the autonomous communities, but in a few areas they share these powers as could be all topics related to medicine, environmental or taxes. In the field of Genomics there is no distribution of powers between State and Autonomous Communities in the Constitution. Under this situation genomics and genetics can be regulated by both. Normally State regulation is about general regulation of one topic and Autonomous Communities the administration on this topic if the Autonomous Communities has the power. This is the case of genomics in medicine or agriculture. Biobanks, for example, are in both regulated. State regulation takes the international norms and integrate it in the Spanish law system, but the administration of this Biobank in the public health system is regulated, from an administrative point of view, in the Autonomous Community. General principles, concept, how it works will be designated by the State, the need and right to consent, etc. and administrative staff, coordination, processes of consent, etc. will be regulated by the Autonomous Community.

In Spain there are four kinds of Acts, Ley Orgánica, Ley, Real Decreto Ley and Real Decreto Legislativo that come from the Parliament. Also, we have norms that come from the Government (regulations) with different names, as could be Real Decreto, Orden ministerial or Orden de Comisión.

Spain has a monist tradition. It is needed that the International Treaty were published in the State Official Bulletin (Boletín Oficial del Estado).

1.2 Spain and United Nations

Spain is a member of the UNO since 1955 and as other countries follow its recommendations and international Treaties³.

The list of treaties that Spain has ratified include

- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights in 1977⁴
- International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights in 1977⁵

1.3 Spain and UNESCO

Spain is a member of the UNESCO since 1953. Its international Declarations, Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights, and International Declaration on Human Genetic Data has

³ <https://www.efedocanalisis.com/noticia/1955-espana-ingresa-onu/>

⁴ Instrumento de ratificación de España del Pacto institucional de Derechos civiles y políticos, 1977, Ratification of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights <https://boe.es/boe/dias/1977/04/30/pdfs/A09337-09343.pdf>

⁵ Instrumento de ratificación de España del Pacto institucional de Derechos Económicos, Sociales y Culturales, 1977, Ratification of the International Covenant on Economics, Social and Cultural Rights <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/1977/04/30/pdfs/A09343-09347.pdf>

been integrated in the Spanish law system by the Biomedica Research Act⁶ of 2007⁷, Police Database on DNA identifications Act of 2007⁸ and the Royal Decree 1716/2011 that establish the basic requirements of authorization and functioning of Biobank with aim on biomedical research and the treatment of biological human samples and regulates the functioning and organization of the National Register of Biobank for biomedical research⁹.

1.4 Spain and OECD

Spain is a member of the OECD since 1961

Spain has ratified the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms in 1978

1.5 Spain and CoE

Spain has ratified the ECHR in 1979¹⁰.

Spain has signed and ratified the Oviedo Convention in 1999. It is in force from 2000¹¹.

About the Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, concerning Biomedical Research, Spain has not signed it and not ratified it¹². There are several conflicts between human rights and this protocol, e. g. The Spanish Mental Health Confederation considers its content is discriminatory with psychosocial disable people, does not make a distinction between coercion and cares between others¹³.

The Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine concerning Genetic Testing for Health Purposes, Spain has not signed it and not ratified it¹⁴.

⁶ Spain, Ley 14/2007 de investigación Biomédica, (Biomedica Research Act), 3 june 2007 <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2007/BOE-A-2007-12945-consolidado.pdf>

⁷ Bobo Ruiz, Jesús. "Condiciones legales y administrativas para la secuenciación del genoma humano en el ámbito militar" Sanid. Mil. Vol. 71 n2 Madrid, abr./jun. 2015 http://scielo.isciii.es/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S1887-85712015000200010 visited 24/10/2018

⁸ Spain, Ley Orgánica 10/2007 reguladora de la base de datos policial sobre identificadores obtenidos a partir del ADN, 8 october 2007, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2007/BOE-A-2007-17634-consolidado.pdf>

⁹ <http://www.catedraderechoygenomahumano.es/images/novedades/RDBiobancos.pdf>

¹⁰ Instrumento de ratificación del Convenio para la Protección de los Derechos Humanos y de las Libertades Fundamentales, Ratification of the European Convention on Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, <https://www.boe.es/buscar/doc.php?id=BOE-A-1979-24010>

¹¹ Instrumento de Ratificación del Convenio para la protección de los derechos humanos y la dignidad del ser humanos con respecto a la aplicación de la Biología y la Medicina, Ratification of Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/1999/10/20/pdfs/A36825-36830.pdf>

¹² Chart of signatures and ratifications of Treaty 195 https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/195/signatures?p_auth=AgDiwDeT

¹³ Asociación Española de Neuropsiquiatría-Profesionales de la Salud Mental, <http://aen.es/wp-content/uploads/2017/12/Posicionamiento-AEN-sobre-Protocolo-Convenio-de-Oviedo.pdf>

¹⁴ Chart of signatures and ratifications of Treaty 203 https://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/203/signatures?p_auth=AgDiwDeT

2 Objectives of the report

The **objective** of this report is to review the state of the law and current legal responses to developments in genetics and genomics and determine how specific legal questions/issues are addressed in Spain. In the Task 2.2 of the SIENNA project we are going to answer six questions related to genetics and genomics.

Although Spain has not a specific Act for genetics and genomics. Near all Acts about the topics have been developed because of international standards and treaties that Spain has signed. So depending on the question we provide a different approach to the topic.

For a specific topic as genetics and genomics there is not a lot of legal academic publications. There are but normally connected with international law or to ethics codes as a lege ferenda study.

This report aims to examine Spain regulatory responses to the questions relating to genetics and genomics as specified in SIENNA task 2.2. In particular, it examines:

- Q 1 how human germline gene editing is regulated in Spain.
- Q 2 Genetic screening in general
- Q 3 Genetic testing in general
- Q 4 Prenatal testing/screening
- Q 5 Newborn screening
- Q 6 Advertising of genetic testing or screening

In addressing these six questions, we also have look for the current legal academic publication in Spain connected to the 6 questions above. For that we had to open the research scope to look for more generic papers about genetic and genomics. The legal chaos in this area needs a bit of flexibility and pick small pieces about the topics in different laws and acts and a variety of legal academic literature.

3. Approach, materials and method

The **methodology** used was a web scanner (google, Dialnet plus, Congreso de los Diputados and BOE¹⁵) for laws, in the last ten years, that regulate the specific topics about genetics and genomics that are developed in the State of the art in deliverable 2.1 of the SIENNA project and the result was that we found no one specific law. We have looked for, in Spanish, terms as “genética”, “genoma”, “edición genética”, “análisis genético”, “test genético”, “recién nacido pruebas”, “pre-natal pruebas”, “publicidad de test genéticos”, “anuncios test genéticos”, all of them with a combination with “legislación” and “regulación”) In google it was needed to add the term “España” to don’t get result linked to South American countries.

There are no Non-legislative Motions (Proposición no de ley)¹⁶ to the Government to start the debate. We also asked to select Spanish experts in the field of medicine and legal scholars and they gave us information about the relevant general health legislation.

¹⁵ Dialnet plus is a Law and social sciences web portal for journals and books <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/> BOE is the Official newspaper where all laws from Spain are published www.boe.es The official site of the Parliament (Congreso de los Diputados) gives information about the state of all legislative work in progress www.congreso.es

¹⁶ This is a resource that the opposition parties can use at the Parliament to incite the Government to start a new regulation.

3.1 Literature overview

To look for literature we have used google scholar and Dialnet plus. The terms used were *genética, genoma, análisis genético, test genético, recién nacido pruebas, pre-natal pruebas, publicidad de test genéticos, anuncios test genéticos*.

3.2 Legal developments

To find legal developments, it has been using the website of the Congreso de los Diputados and the web of the State Official Bulletin where can be found new proposal of legal motions and track the last changes and version of the Acts.

3.3 Analysis of legislation for 6 specific questions on genetics and genomics

The legal approach has been hard. There is no specific legislation on genetics or genomics in Spain. There are several Acts that can regulate all around genetics. Probably the nucleus of all of them is the Biomedical Research Act, which the last version is from 2011. But to reach all the questions for task 2.2 we need to consult more than 8 different Acts.

4. Scope and Limitations of this report

This report focuses on the legal analysis of Spanish national law in genetics and genomics. The scope is limited to task 2.2 of the SIENNA project limited to time.

We have to solve the problem of a lack of a specific genetic and genomic law, thus we need to use several different legislation, not all of them adapted to the Oviedo convention, to find the solutions of the questions presented. We can say all questions were addressed and, although the answer was not easy, we could find a solution for each one.

Part II current overview of legal academic publications and legal developments in Country Spain

5. Current legal academic debates in the area of genetics and genomics

5.1 Current legal academic debates regarding human germline gene editing

The current legal academic debate regarding human germline gene editing in Spain is around the international context¹⁷, particularly linked to the Oviedo Convention¹⁸. The debate spins on the line were germline gene editing will be allowed or not, particularly when these modifications could be transmitted to the next generation¹⁹.

¹⁷ Bellber Capella, V., “La revolución de edición genética mediante CRISPR-Cas9 y los desafíos éticos y regulatorios que comporta” in *Cuadernos de Bioética*, XXVII, 2016.

¹⁸ Torres Martínez, S. R. and María del Mar Navarro Martínez, “Desafíos éticos y jurídicos de las técnicas de edición del genoma” in *REDC*, vol. 2. n. 2, 2016 p. 4.

¹⁹ Torres Martínez, S. R. and María del Mar Navarro Martínez, “Desafíos éticos y jurídicos de las técnicas de edición del genoma” in *REDC*, vol. 2. n. 2, 2016 p. 6.

There is also the worry of a different regulation and the need of a harmonization of the legal systems²⁰.

5.2 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic screening in general

There are no legal academic debates about genetic screening in Spain. There are some papers about the use of genetic screening in some areas, prison, at the work place²¹ or in a legal trial²², near all linked to the protection of the genetic information and who and how could be used.

5.3 Current legal academic debates regarding genetic testing in general

The legal scholarship is debating how genetic testing for consumers will impact constitutional rights²³. The rights affected will be personal and family privacy, data protection, non-discrimination principle, information rights²⁴. First these genetic tests are considered as other consumer good.

The big majority of the scholars consider that these tests, by the Biomedical Research Act, that have to be done under a medical aim thus there is no possibility to access to them only for curiosity²⁵. We can affirm that they are against the liberalization of this kind of test²⁶.

5.4 Current legal academic debates regarding prenatal testing/screening

The debates about prenatal testing and screening is not very popular in Spanish doctrine. The little we have found it related to the interruption of pregnancy's decision²⁷ and the constitutional rights of the no-born²⁸.

There is no legal reference about the prenatal testing itself. Generic reference of genetics testing in general have comments about it, but very general observations.

5.5 Current legal academic debates regarding newborn screening

The topic is not very popular in the scholar doctrine. As in the other case we have to look for the general approach to find solutions to the debate with newborn screening. In Spain is related to euthanasia from newborns²⁹.

²⁰ García-Llenera, V., "Tradiciones culturales como barreras para un derecho común: el caso de la mejora humana en línea germinal" in *ACFS*, 2017, p. 158.

²¹ Calvo Gallego, F. J., "Test genéticos y vigilancia de la salud del trabajador" in *Derecho y Conocimiento: anuario jurídico sobre la sociedad de la información y del conocimiento*, n2, 2022.

²² Velásquez-Velázquez, F., "Las pruebas genéticas predictivas y el proceso penal" in *Estudios penales y criminológicos*, n 37, 2017.

²³ De Montalvo Jääskeläinen, F., "Test genéticos directos al consumidor y límites al principio de autonomía" in *Derecho y Salud*, vol. 25, 2015, p. 38

²⁴ Juan María, M. O., "La generalización de los test genéticos y su incidencia en los derechos fundamentales" in *Revista europea de derechos fundamentales*, n 29, 2017, p. 241-265.

²⁵ Abellán, F., "Los análisis genéticos dentro de la ley de investigación genética" in *Revista de la escuela médica legal*, june 2019, p. 29.

²⁶ De Montalvo Jääskeläinen, F., "Test genéticos directos al consumidor y límites al principio de autonomía" in *Derecho y Salud*, vol. 25, 2015, p. 49.

²⁷ Souto García, E. M., "Mujer y vida prenatal: ¿dos realidades irreconciliables? Análisis sobre la posible reforma en materia de aborto" in *Anuario da Facultade de Dereito da Universidade da Coruña*, n 13, 2009.

²⁸ Gómez Montoro, A. J., "El estatuto constitucional del no nacido: evolución y situación actual en España" in *Revista de Derecho Político*, UNED, Madrid, n 102, 2018, p. 47-78.

²⁹ Martín Hortigüela, M. E., "Análisis del debate sobre la eutanasia neonatal a través de la literatura actual" in *Cuadernos de bioética*, vol. 26, n 87, 2015.

5.6 Current legal academic debates regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

It was not possible to find any academic reference on this topic.

6. Legal developments in the area of genetics and genomics

6.1 Legal developments regarding human germline gene editing

Spain has signed and ratified the Oviedo Convention in 1999. It is in force of 2000³⁰.

After being in force Spain has a new Act in Biomedical Research of 2007 and has been amended for last time in 2011 to introduce the last innovations.

Related to embryo, pre-embryo and ovocytes it is regulated on Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act since 2006.

About the topics related to human research it is under the scope of The Royal Decree 1090/2015 that regulates Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Comities and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research³¹.

There are no legal developments in human germline gene editing.

6.2 Legal developments regarding genetic screening in general

Genetic screening is regulated in the Biomedical Research Act.

There are no legal developments in genetic screening.

6.3 Legal developments regarding genetic testing in general

Genetic testing in general is regulated in the Biomedical Research Act in general.

In the case of in-vitro diagnosis, genetic testing could be regulated by the Royal Decree 1662/2000 about Health Products for in vitro Diagnosis³².

There are no legal developments in genetic testing.

³⁰ Instrumento de Ratificación del Convenio para la protección de los derechos humanos y la dignidad del ser humanos con respecto a la aplicación de la Biología y la Medicina, Ratification of Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being with regard to the Application of Biology and Medicine: Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/1999/10/20/pdfs/A36825-36830.pdf>

³¹ Spain, Real Decreto 1090/2015 por el que se regulan los ensayos clínicos con medicamentos, los Comités de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos y el Registro Español de Estudios Clínicos, The Royal Decree 1090/2015 that regulates Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Comities and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research, 4 December 2015, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2015/12/24/pdfs/BOE-A-2015-14082.pdf>

³² Spain, Real Decreto 1662/2000, de 29 de septiembre, sobre productos sanitarios para diagnóstico in vitro, Royal Decree 1662/2000 about Health Products for in vitro Diagnosis, 29 September 2000, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2000/09/30/pdfs/A33482-33508.pdf>

6.4 Legal developments regarding prenatal testing/screening

Related to embryo and pre-embryo it is regulated on Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act of 2006. The rest of cases will be regulated by the Biomedical Research Act. Finally, in case of interruption of pregnancy, it is regulated under the Sexual and Reproduction Health and voluntary termination of the pregnancy of 2015.

There are no legal developments in prenatal testing/screening.

6.5 Legal developments regarding newborn screening

New born is regulated under the Biomedical Research Act. Thus, it applies the same as we have in the previous sections.

There are no new legal developments in newborn screening.

6.6 Legal developments regarding advertising of genetic testing or screening

Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim³³.

If we consider the genetic testing as a health product it will be regulated under Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Product Act of 2006³⁴. Last version is from 2015.

There are no new legal developments in advertising of genetic testing or screening.

Part III Specific legal considerations on human genetics and genomics

7. Human germline gene editing

A. Regulation of basic research: The Biomedical Research Act, from 2007, and Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act, from 2006. The first Act lets use embryos (embryo is defined as a fecund ovocyte that is inside the uterus, article 3. l) if they have lost their ability of biological develop and if they are dead (article 31.1 that refers to article 28.1 of the same Act). The law demands from a facultative member to determinate this situation.

The law also talks about pre-embryo (discusses by the doctrine whether there is a difference between both or not) understood as an embryo generated in vitro that formed by a group of cells as a result of the progressive division of the ovocyte until the first 14 days (article 3.s. of the Biomedical Research Act).

³³ Spain, Real decreto 1907/1996 sobre publicidad y promoción comercial de productos, actividades Servicios con pretendida finalidad sanitaria (Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim), 2 August 1996, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/1996/08/06/pdfs/A24322-24325.pdf>

³⁴ Spain, Real Decreto Legislativo 1/2015 por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley de garantías y uso racional de los medicamentos y productos sanitarios (Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Product Act), 24 July 2015, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2015/07/25/pdfs/BOE-A-2015-8343.pdf>

The law system makes a distinction between obtaining and research. Obtaining it is forbidden to build a human embryo or pre-embryo with exclusive research aim (article 33 of the Biomedical Research Act). We can understand that gene editing with the idea to build an embryo is forbidden. As well, it is allowed to get stem cells for therapeutic and research aims, but not whether for that purpose you have to build an embryo.

It is possible to experiment and research with oocytes and pre-embryos, which are the rest of an assisted reproduction process (article 32 of the Biomedical Research Act that refers to Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act, articles 14-16). Normally you have three oocytes (article 3.2 of the Assisted Reproduction Technics Act). If there are no longer needed for reproduction they can be used following the Assisted Reproduction Technics Act of 2006. Article 14 of this Act says that the gametes could be used to research but, in that case, must not be used for procreation or implanted in a woman. Article 15 regulates the use of pre-embryos in research or experimentation needs the consent of the woman and, in case, her couple of hands; the pre-embryo should not be developed in vitro more than 14 days; have to be done in an authorized center; the research has to be under the scope of a project; and in case of transfer of pre-embryo to another centre, always under a research project. The ethical principles always ruled by a suitability, feasibility, and pertinence principles.

All research with this genetic material have to be approved by the Spanish Bioethics Committee (Title VII of the Biomedical Research Act).

In general, there is a prohibition of gene manipulation. In the Spanish Criminal Code it can be found a felony about Gen editing (article 159 and ff.)

B. Regulation of pre-clinical research: Pre-clinic

There is no legal definition of pre-clinical.

The use of animals on gene editing is regulated by the Royal Decree 53/2013 that establish the basic norms apply for protection of animals used for experimental and other research aims, included lecturing. In general, it is allowed to use animals in research procedures. Article 5 lets only to use animals in fundamental research, applied research and scientific methods to these aims: a) prevention, prophylaxis, diagnosis and treatment of illness, bad health or other anomalies or their effects on human beings, animals or plants; b) assessment, detection, regulation or modification of the philological condition of human beings, animals or plants and c) animal wellness. Also in the development and fabrication of pharmaceutical products, foods, feed or other substance or products. Protection of the environment and animal species. Finally, teaching and, in particular, legal medicine and forensics.

In particular, apes are regulated in article 21 of the Royal Decree and it is not allowed to use some species of apes and those regulated in Annex A of the Regulatory 338/97 of the Council of 9th December 1996, except in these conditions: a) prevent, avoid, diagnostic or treatment of disable illness or that could potentially put human life in danger or b) it is scientifically justified that there is no other way to get the aim of the investigation.

Other apes are not allowed to use them, except it is scientifically justified that there is no other way to get the aim of the investigation or the procedural has an aim of the article 5 letter b and c with aims of prevention, prophylaxis, diagnosis and treatment of illness, bad health or other anomalies or their effects on human beings; and fundamental research and protections of the species.

C. Regulation of clinical research in humans: The Royal Decree 1090/2015 that regulates Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Comities and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research³⁵ is integrated into Spanish law because of Regulatory (EU) 536/2014. For that reason the definitions are exactly the same as in the European Law there is nothing new (article 2.i of the Royal Decree 1090/2015). The same happens with Low-intervention clinical trial (article 2.j) and with non-Interventional study (article 2.k).

Article 17.3 of the Royal Decree prohibit clinical research with genic therapy drugs, which produce modifications in the person's germline's genic identity.

D. Regulation of clinical applications: Normal clinical practice is defined in article 2.m of the Royal Decree, the same as the European Regulatory (EU) 536/2014. Article 17.3 of the Royal Decree prohibits clinical research with genetic therapy drugs, which produce modifications in the person's germline's genic identity.

About initiating pregnancy with edited embryos or whit edited gametes the Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act of 2006, in article 12, let, to the authorized centre, to practice technics of pre-implant diagnosis for the detection of serious heritage illness³⁶ that is not postnatal treatable of to detect other alterations that can compromise the viability of the embryo. Article 13 says any intervention with a therapeutic aim over the pre-embryo in vitro will be allowed only if the aim it to treat an illness or to prevent it with reasonable and contrast warrants. The requirements for that are: a) information to the woman and her couple about the diagnosis, procedures and risks; b) that the pathology with a serious or very serious prognosis has a diagnosis that has reasonable possibilities of cure or improvement; c) no change the heritage characteristics that are not pathologic and do not look for race or individual selection; and d) the procedure has to be in an authorized health centre. It is needed an authorization from the competent health authority and positive report from the National Commission of Human Assisted Reproduction.

8. Genetic screening in general

Article 9.3 of the Biomedical Research Act of 2007 allows genetic screening to predict genetic illness, identify to a subject as a carrier of a gene that can be responsible of illness. In case of detection of a predisposition to an illness or a genetic susceptibility as well as to study the inter-individual response to drugs or genetic-environmental. The last possibility is the study illness' molecular basis

We can find in the Biomedical Research Act of 2007 the general regulation in Title V. It regulates the basic principles of genetic screening and in what cases can be used (basically to avoid a genetic illness) the kind of information that has to be given to the patient and how he/she will be consent. The basic principles are: a) accessibility and equality; b) data protection; c) free of charge; d) consent; and e) use of data (article 44). About the information given to the patient article 47 of the Biomedical Research Act establish that has to be included the aim of the genetic analysis, place where it would be take place

³⁵ Spain, Real Decreto 1090/2015, por el que se regulan los ensayos clínicos con medicamentos, los Comités de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos y el Registro Español de Estudios Clínicos (Royal Decree 1090/2015 that regulates Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Comities and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research), 4 December 2015, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2015/12/24/pdfs/BOE-A-2015-14082.pdf>

³⁶ This is considered as unclear concept that can change from each Autonomous Community. Jiménez González, J., "Definición de conceptos jurídicos vs. listado de enfermedades susceptibles como soluciones respecto al uso de diagnóstico genético preimplantacional" in *Bioderecho*, n 6, 2016, p 2.

and destiny of the biological sample, persons authorized to access to the results when they are not dissociated or anonymized, warning of the possibility of unexpected discovery that could be important to the patient, warning of the implication that could have for the patient's relatives and the convenient that he/she transmit this information to them and, finally the compromise to provide genetic advice. The regulation about consent can be found in article 48 that have to be expressed and specific by hand. In article 50 of the regulation that we are studying can be found which medical personnel is allowed to deal with this data. In the next articles are regulated the secure measures around the use of this genetic information.

Also in the Autonomous Communities is regulated the genetic screening. Spain has a public health system that is managed by these Communities. For example, Andalusia has its own regulation, Act 11/2007 that regulated the Genetic Council, the protection of the person's rights who has a genetic screening and Biobank³⁷. Normally these norms are to regulate the administrative action and manage the public health system.

Screening provider's responsibilities are regulated in both acts. The Biomedical Research Act of 2007, Title VI, imposes administrative sanctions from 600€ up to 1.000.000€ from different kinds of actions. It makes three groups of actions that can be classified as very serious, serious and minor (article 72.5). As a minor sanction is considered any breach on the duties or violation of the prohibitions established by the Biomedical Research Act (Article 74.2.A). Serious infraction are a) any breach of any previous prescription, condition, requirement and authorization establish by the Biomedical Research Act refer to the registers needed; b) any omission of data, consents and references require by this norm; c) the absence of supply of data to the health authority in charge of the register; d) breach of the confidential conditions; e) infringement of the free of charge of donation of pre-embryo, embryo and foetus; and f) infringement of the norms and warrants for the transfer of cells and tissue from human embryos to other countries (article 74.2.B). Finally, very serious infraction are: a) any intervention drove to the introduction of a genetic modification in the descendants; b) keep the pre-embryo's develop in vitro for more than 14 days; c) keep life embryo or foetus outside the utero with any aim different of procreation; d) extraction of embryo or foetus' cells or tissues from the placenta or its cover with an aim different from diagnosis or therapeutic not allowed by the Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act; e) in case of the prohibition of embryo and pre-embryo constitution with an exclusive aim of experimentation; f) production of hybrids that use human genetic material, except what it is allowed by the Human Assisted Reproduction Technics Act; and g) the breach of the prescriptions, condition, requirements or authorisations needed by law to obtain and use of cells and tissues from human embryo and other similar (article 74).

The Andalusian Act over the Genetic Council, Protection of Persons Been Subject of a Genetic Testing and DNA Bank in Andalusia rules minor, serious and very serious infractions. The first one is any breach on the duties or violation of the prohibitions established by this act; serious ones are a) to carry out genetic screening without authorization of the research project; b) use of biological samples without the consent; c) use of biological samples with different aims as the authorized ones; d) pay to obtain biological samples; and e) carry out a genetic sifting without an autorotation; and very serious ones are: a) carry out genetic screening with different aims as health assistant or biomedical research; and

³⁷ Spain, Ley 11/2007 reguladora del consejo genético, de protección de los derechos de las personas que se sometan a análisis genéticos y de los bancos de ADN humano en Andalucía (Act 11/2007 that regulated the Genetic Council, the protection of person's rights who has a genetic screening and Biobank of Andalusia), 26 november 2007, <https://www.juntadeandalucia.es/boja/2007/246/2>

b) the use of data obtained from genetic screening with different aims as health assistant or biomedical research. These actions can be fined from 6.000€ up to 1.000.000€. Normally these actions have to be committed in the Andalusian health service and the national law use to be applied in no public health services or research centres not linked to Andalusian administration.

There are also different felonies linked to genetic manipulation with humans and with the liberation of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) with penalties up to 10 years imprisonment (articles 159-162 of the Penal Code).

9. Genetic testing in general

Genetic testing outside the health system are not regulated in Spain right now. Article 9.3 of the Biomedical Research Act says that genetic test could be done only to predict a genetic illness, to identify a subject as a carrier of a gene responsible of an illness or to detect a predisposition or susceptibility of a genetic illness with a medical aim or for medical research and with genetic advise. As it doesn't follow the restrictions of the Biomedical Research Act should be sanctioned under article 74 of the Biomedical Research Act.

About genetic testing for an in vitro diagnostic The Royal Decree 1662/2000 about Health Products for in vitro Diagnosis³⁸ prohibits the advertising of this kind of products and should be used only by health professionals (article 25.7). In case of a breach of this ban the sanction will be a fine regulated in article 29.4, 9 and 12, considered as a serious infraction and ruled by article 36 of the General Health Act from 1986.

10. Prenatal testing/screening

There is regulated the possibility to use technics to detect hereditary illness, early (premature) illness that are not possible to cure and detect other alterations that can be dangerous for the pre-embryo and before implant it (article 12 of the Assisted Reproduction Technics Act from 2006)³⁹.

This regulation has to be complete with the general rules about genetics screening from the Biomedical Research Act mention above. Prenatal testing it is regulated in article 9.3 of the Biomedical Research Act, a general regulation of genetic screening can be found in article 44, 45, 46 and 47 (object of the genetic test, basic principles, information and consent) all mentioned above.

Non-invasive pre-natal testing are not mentioned, but Title II of the Act mentions invasive procedures, thus can be understood that the rest is Non-invasive. We have only one mention in the Biomedical Research Act in article 53 about genetic screening in pre-embryo, embryo or foetus, only to emphasise that the result of the screening will be under the principles of data protection and confidentiality.

Abortion in Spain is regulated by the Sexual and Reproduction Health and voluntary termination of the pregnancy of 2015. Abortion is free in the first 14 weeks (article 14). In case of a health condition, always when there is a high risk for the life or health of the mother, there is a risk of serious anomalies

³⁸ Spain, Real Decreto 1662/2000, sobre productos sanitarios para diagnóstico in vitro, Royal Decree 1662/2000 about Health Products for in vitro Diagnosis, 29 September 2000, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/2000/09/30/pdfs/A33482-33508.pdf>.

³⁹ Romeo Casabona, C., "El principio de no discriminación y las restricciones relativas a la realización del análisis genéticos (Capítulo IV)" in Carlos Romeo Casabona, *El Convenio de Derechos Humanos y Biomedicina. Su entrada en vigor en el ordenamiento jurídico español*, Granada, Comares, 2002. p. 183.

in the foetus it is possible to interrupt the pregnancy in the first 22 weeks. If there are anomalies incompatible with the life at any time (article 15).

The woman has to be informed at any time about the illness and risks also about the procedure and it needs her consent (article 17 and article 13).

11 Newborn screening

Yes, as general screening, as we have said before related to the Biomedical Research Act of 2007.

In case of new-born consent obtained by its representative, in general the parents (Article 4 of Biomedical Research Act of 2007).

In Andalusian, article 6 has a similar procedural by representation.

The conditions or the use of data and samples should be used only for the reason that the consent is given (article 4). It is forbidden to use the data for another purpose different as the one consented (article 5).

Data can be stored for 5 years. After this period the patient has the right to delete it. In case he/she does not use this right the data will be stored for the time needed to preserve the health of the patient or third persons related to him/her. Outside these cases the data can be conserved for research when it is anonymized (article 52).

In the case of samples, they can be conserved with the consent of the patient (article 61). There is no time limit in the Act. For research purposes, they can be saved for the aim of the research except the patient has consented to use it for other research purposes. This consent has to be explicit.

12. Advertising of genetic testing or screening

There is no distinction between health and non-health genetic testing or screening.

About genetic testing for an in vitro diagnostic The Real Decreto 1662/2000 prohibits the advertising of this kind of kits (article 29.2.4, 9 and 12).

In case of other products, activities or services with a health goal, we should go to the Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim⁴⁰, about their advertising. Article 1 says that the Health Authorities will control the advertisement of products, material, substances, energies or methods that adversities or are presented as useful for diagnosis, prevention or treatment of illness or physiological develop, weight loss, physical or physiologic modification, restoration, correction or modification of the organic functions or other health aims (article 1).

It is prohibited any secret remedies and its publicity (article 2).

⁴⁰ Spain, Real Decreto 1907/1996 sobre publicidad y promoción comercial de productos, actividades o servicios con pretendida finalidad sanitaria. (Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim), 2 August 1996, <https://www.boe.es/boe/dias/1996/08/06/pdfs/A24322-24325.pdf>

In article 3 there is a ban of publicity of many cases, but the goal of the task 2.2 of the SIENNA project point 15 says that any product that pretend to replace the consult or intervention of a health professional are banned.

If we consider the genetic testing or screening as a health product, advertising of this kind of products is regulated under article 78. 6 and 7 of the Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Product Act of 2006. It is prohibited any direct or indirect advertising of health products if they are granted by the National Health System and health products, which are destined to be used only by health professionals.

Finally, all elements for the analysis, cotton buds, etc., are regulated by the Royal Decree 1662/2000, articles 6 and 7. The Spanish Drug Agencies should be informed. But is only for authorised health personnel and not for consumers.

For non-health purposes, there is no regulation. We can consider that they are banned, but it is not clear.

Part IV Discussion and conclusions

13. Discussion

To address the six questions we could find enough information in the scholar doctrine but not plenty. It is not a big surprise because there are not many doctors and lawyers with a multidisciplinary approach to the topics. In many cases the reference where doctors that comment the law or layers who make an approach from the international regulation from a moral point of view, but very few get into the point on how should be regulated. That could be because many of them are scholar from catholic universities.

Unfortunately, there is no genetic or genomic Act. To have the solution, it was needing an approach to several acts to find the answer to the question. One of the problem is that to find the solution we need to play with two or three norms before and after the Oviedo declaration. This makes that some of the solutions are an approach, but not an exact answer.

Spain as a catholic tradition country has some taboos about the possibility to be good or stay near god. This means that many of the scholars who have studied the topics are sceptic on allow to use these technics or the possibility that a person has the possibility to access to his own genomic.

The big gab, as usually when we talk about law, is that genomic and genetic technics go faster as the regulation. In any case, as is has been commented before, have six, seven different acts, some of them from last century, makes difficult to approach to new problems.

Taking into consideration how important will be genetic and genomic, it would be interesting to have a general Act about these topics. As well the information given to the patient and how he/she consent. Probably, to have these kinds of protocols should be regulated in the hard law and not only in the soft law or deontological codes.

In Spain the legal changes in genetics and genomics are driven by the international regulations. Otherwise the tendency in the legal doctrine, as we have seen in the report, is to ban the use of genetics or at least to limit it.

The impact of this technology on Human Rights in Spain could be big.

In Art. 10.1 of the Spanish Constitution⁴¹ can be found the right to a personal dignity and free human development understood as the personal freedom to be what a person wants to be, that means should be treated not as an instrument but as an end in himself/herself⁴². Dignity right can be considered relative and difficult to precise, for that reason the normal approach to its material content is from the negative aspects, the absence of dignity, this negative aspect of dignity is considered an infringement of the right (when there is no dignity)⁴³: it is easier to know when there is no dignity than the definition of this concept itself. Thus, it depends in which context it will have a different meaning.

Once we see the difficulty to understand the concept and the topic we are working with, we can say dignity, related to genetics and genomics, as the human being's quality that let them to have possessed rights and this means the demand of collection of minimum that refer to humiliation verge and subhumanity conditions⁴⁴. In this context, we can say that some genetics or genomics can have a direct impact in the personal dignity, particularly for good and in other cases of bad.

The second important article for our report, article 15 of the Spanish constitution⁴⁵, talks about the life right. This is under discussion if foetus should be protected or not. Embryos should not be included in the protection of this article but any doctrine considered embryos as a life in potency. The end of life the limits are the end of brain activity or cardiac pulse. In particular about the use of CRISPR in embryos to save the life could be included in this protection.

Art. 14 of the Spanish Constitution regulates the right to equality, therefore no discrimination principle is included in this principle⁴⁶. This article talks expressly about some kinds of discriminations: birth, race, sex, religion, opinion and, finally, lets a door open to future ways of discrimination linked to any other personal or social condition or circumstance. This article does not prohibit all different of threats, but only that one that discriminate⁴⁷, thus, it is possible to use genetics always when there is no discrimination. Thus a person could use it, whether there is no discriminatory impact in other people e.g. genetic manipulation to get better skills as normal people, in particular, in competition with others.

⁴¹ Article 10.1: The human dignity, the inviolable and inherent rights, the free development of the personality, the respect for the law and for the rights of others are the foundation of political order and social peace. English version of the Spanish Constitution can be found in https://www.boe.es/legislacion/codigos/codigo.php?id=158_Constitucion_Espanola_____The_Spanish_Constitution_&modo=1

⁴² Prieto Álvarez, Tomás, *La dignidad personal*, Thomson-Civitas, Madrid, 2005, p.169.

⁴³ Pascual Medrano, Amalia, "La dignidad humana como principio jurídico del ordenamiento constitucional español" in Chueca, R., *Dignidad humana y derecho fundamental*, Centro de estudios políticos y constitucionales, Madrid, 2015, p. 306

⁴⁴ Ruiz Lapeña, Rosa María, "La dignidad y sus manifestaciones en el ordenamiento constitucional español" in Ricardo Luis Chueca Rodríguez, *Dignidad humana y derecho fundamental*, Centro de estudios políticos y constitucionales, Madrid, 2015, p. 337

⁴⁵ Article 15: Everyone has the right to life and to a physical and moral integrity, and may under no circumstances be subjected to torture or to inhuman or degrading punishment or treatment. The death penalty is hereby abolished, except as provided by military criminal law in times of war.

⁴⁶ Article 14: Spaniards are equal before the law and may not in any way be discriminated against on account of birth, race, sex, religion, opinion or any other personal or social condition or circumstance.

⁴⁷ Naranjo de la Cruz, Rafael "Derechos fundamentales" in Miguel Agudo Zamora et al. *Manual de Derecho Constitucional*, Tecnos, Madrid, 2018, p. 463.

There is no many cases in the Constitutional Court about equality principle and health treatment and no one related to genetics or genomics manipulations.

Art. 43⁴⁸ talks about a political principle of how Government decision should have in mind to regulate public health service, especially focus on how the public health system should operate: prevention measures, service needs and benefices. Finally announces, that Government will provide health education, sport and facilities the proper use of leisure and free time. This principle has two sides: a) the preventive health or collective health and b) the individual right. So the Government has to have an active power to avoid illness and the citizen have the right to get medical treatment⁴⁹. That could be interpreted as the Government should make an effort to avoid illness and genetic modification or testing is a key technology for this aim.

Privacy right in Spanish constitution is regulated under article 18⁵⁰. This year there is another decision of the Constitutional Court about article 18 (1) where honour, personal and family privacy and self-image. The same article in paragraph 4 limits the use of computer use and data processing to protect this right, a particular sensitive area for genetic and genomics. From 23rd November 2018 there is a new Data Protection and Digital Rights Warranties⁵¹ and there is, as we have seen above, special restrictions in the Research Biomedical Act.

14. Conclusions

Spain, can we say, has a regulation of all the questions addressed in task 2.2 of the SIENNA project. Gene editing is already actualized to the last and most important international standards. In case of embryo and prenatal editing the regulation does not talk explicit to genetic screening or testing, but these cases could be integrated in the general provision, although it could be interesting to update the legislation to new technics.

The nucleus of gene editing is the Biosanitary Research Act, which also applies to the rest of genetic and genomic issues. Probably it would be better just to make some change to be clear, that is for all scopes of genetic and genomic use.

⁴⁸ Article 14: 1. The right to health protection is recognised.

2. It is incumbent upon the public authorities to organise and safeguard public health by means of preventive measures and the necessary benefits and services. The law shall establish the rights and duties of all concerned in this respect.

3. The public authorities shall promote health education, physical education and sport. Likewise, they shall encourage the proper use of leisure time.

⁴⁹ Porras Nadas, Antonio, “Los principios rectores de la política social y económica” in Miguel Agudo Zamora et al. *Manual de Derecho Constitucional*, Tecnos, Madrid, 2018, p. 632

⁵⁰ Article 18: 1. The right to honour, to personal and family privacy and to the own image is guaranteed.

2. The home is inviolable. No entry or search may be made without the consent of occupant or a legal warrant, except in case of flagrante delicto.

3. Secrecy of communications is guaranteed, particular of postal, telegraphic and telephonic communications, except the event of a court order to the contrary.

4. The law shall limit the use of data processing in order to guarantee the honour and personal and family privacy of citizens and the full exercise of their rights.

⁵¹ Spain, Proyecto de Ley orgánica de protección de datos y garantías de los derechos digitales (Act Project on Data Protection and Digital Rights Warranties), 2018, http://www.senado.es/legis12/publicaciones/pdf/senado/bocg/BOCG_D_12_289_2209.PDF

As we have commented on this report many of the issues are regulated in a very general way. As the needs of the society, in particular in a so sensible aspect as could be the use of genetic and genomic in medicine, it would be needed a more specific develop of the regulation to ensure the conflict with its use.

In general, we can say that Spain regulate these topics with a reasonable level, particularly because of the international standards. We have to say that the impulse to regulate genetics and genomic come from international level and not because of the internal debate for that reason we can say that Spain is in the average of the western countries. Probably, because of the legal literature, the scope of the legal developments in genetics would be different, likely more restrictive.

References

International law

- International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights
- International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights
- International Declaration on Human Genetic Data
- Universal Declaration on the Human Genome and Human Rights
- Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms
- European Convention on Human Rights
- Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine
- Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine
- The Additional Protocol to the Convention on Human Rights and Biomedicine concerning Genetic Testing for Health Purposes

National law

- Spain, Ley 14/2007 de investigación Biomédica, (Biomedica Research Act), 3 June 2007
- Spain, Real Decreto 1090/2015 por el que se regulan los ensayos clínicos con medicamentos, los Comités de Ética de la Investigación con medicamentos y el Registro Español de Estudios Clínicos, The Royal Decree 1090/2015 that regulates Clinical Trials with Drugs, Drugs Research Ethics Comities and the Spanish Register of Clinical Research, 4 December 2015
- Spain, Real Decreto 1662/2000, de 29 de septiembre, sobre productos sanitarios para diagnóstico in vitro, Royal Decree 1662/2000 about Health Products for in vitro Diagnosis, 29 September 2000
- Spain, Ley 11/2007 reguladora del consejo genético, de protección de los derechos de las personas que se sometan a análisis genéticos y de los bancos de ADN humano en Andalucía (Act 11/2007 that regulated the Genetic Council, the protection of person's rights who has a genetic screening and Biobank of Andalusia), 26 november 2007
- Spain, Real decreto 1907/1996, sobre publicidad y promoción comercial de productos, actividades Servicios con pretendida finalidad sanitaria (Royal Decree 1907/1996 over Publicity and Commercial Promotion of Product, Activities or Service with Health Aim), 2 August 1996
- Spain, Real Decreto Legislativo 1/2015 por el que se aprueba el texto refundido de la Ley de garantías y uso racional de los medicamentos y productos sanitarios (Warranties and Rational Use of Drugs and Health Product Act), 24 July 2015
- Spain, Proyecto de Ley orgánica de protección de datos y garantías de los derechos digitales (Act Project on Data Protection and Digital Rights Warranties), 2018
- Spain, Código penal (Criminal Code), 23 November 1995
- Spain, Constitución Española (Spaish Constitution), 29 December 1978

- Spain, Royal Decree 53/2013 that establish the basic norms apply to protection of animals used on experimentation and other research aims, included lecturing. In general, it is allowed to use animals in research procedures.

Literature

- Abellán, F., “Los análisis genéticos dentro de la ley de investigación genética” in *Revista de la escuela médica legal*, june 2019
- Bellber Capella, V., “La revolución de edición genética mediante CRISPR-Cas9 y los desafíos éticos y regulatorios que comporta” in *Cuadernos de Bioética*, XXVII 2016
- Calvo Gallego, F. J., “Test genéticos y vigilancia de la salud del trabajador” in *Derecho y Conocimiento: anuario jurídico sobre la sociedad de la información y del conocimiento*, n2, 2022
- De Montalvo Jääskeläinen, F., “Test genéticos directos al consumidor y límites al principio de autonomía” in *Derecho y Salud*, vol. 25, 2015
- Garcia-Llenera, V., “Tradiciones culturales como barreras para un derecho común: el caso de la mejora humana en línea germinal” in *ACFS*, 2017
- Gómez Montoro, A. J., “El estatuto constitucional del no nacido: evolución y situación actual en España” in *Revista de Derecho Político*, UNED, Madrid, n 102, 2018
- Jiménez González, J., “Definición de conceptos jurídicos vs. listado de enfermedades susceptibles como soluciones respecto al uso de diagnóstico genético preimplantacional” in *Bioderecho*, n 6, 2016
- Martín Hortigüela, M. E., “Análisis del debate sobre la eutanasia neonatal a través de la literatura actual” in *Cuadernos de bioética*, vol. 26, n 87, 2015
- Martínez Otero, J. M. “La generalización de los test genéticos y su incidencia en los derechos fundamentales” in *Revista europea de derechos fundamentales*, n 29, 2017
- Torres Martínez, S., and María del Mar Navarro Martínez, “Desafíos éticos y jurídicos de las técnicas de edición del genoma” in *REDC*, vol. 2. n. 2, 2016
- Romeo Casabona, C., “El principio de no discriminación y las restricciones relativas a la realización del análisis genéticos (Capítulo IV)” in Romeo Casabona, C. *El Convenio de Derechos Humanos y Biomedicina. Su entrada en vigor en el ordenamiento jurídico español*, Granada, Comares, 2002
- Romeo Malanda, S., “Análisis genéticos directos al consumidor: su régimen jurídico en el ordenamiento jurídico español y propuestas de actuación” in Carlos María Romeo Casabona (ed.), *Hacia una nueva medicina: consejo genético*, Granada, Comares, 2013
- Souto García, E. M., “Mujer y vida prenatal: ¿dos realidades irreconciliables? Análisis sobre la posible reforma en materia de aborto” in *Anuario da Facultade de Dereito da Universidade da Coruña*, n 13, 2009
- Velasquez-Velazquez, F., “Las pruebas genéticas predictivas y el proceso penal” in *Estudios penales y criminológicos*, n 37, 2017